

The Structure of Xylotenin, a New Furanocoumarin from *Chloroxylon swietenia* DC*

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Extraction of the leaves of *Chloroxylon swietenia* DC (*Rutaceae*) has furnished bergapten, isopimpinellin, heliottin and a new furanocoumarin, named xylotenin, $C_{16}H_{14}O_5$, M^+ 254, m.p. 91-92°, for which we suggest the structure (I).

The molecular formula of xylotenin (I) was confirmed by accurate mass measurement[†] (found : 254.0944 ; calc. : 254.0943). Comparison of its UV spectrum [λ_{max} (ethanol) 246 m μ (log ϵ , 4.37), 292 (4.09) and 326 (3.92) ; λ_{min} 225 (4.17), 267 (3.73) and 317 (3.89) ; unaffected by addition of base suggesting the absence of phenolic hydroxyl group] with those of psoralene¹ and angelicin² indicated that xylotenin had a linear furanocoumarin system. The IR spectrum showed ν_{max} (nujol) 1710 (coumarin lactone ring), 1625 (aromatic), 1580 (α -pyrone double bond) and 880 cm^{-1} (very strong ; terminal methylene, out-of-plane bending)³. The NMR spectrum (60 Mc/sec. in $CDCl_3$) of xylotenin, in which all the fourteen protons were assigned, provided further evidence for the presence of a furan ring fused linearly to the coumarin nucleus. A first order analysis of the aromatic zone of the spectrum revealed a singlet proton at C-8 (T 2.60), a doublet proton at C-5 (T 2.36 splitting probably due to long range coupling with the 3' proton, $J_{H_8'-H_5} = 1$ c./sec.), a quartet furan 3' proton (T 3.21, $J_{H_2'-H_3} = 2.5$ c./sec.), a doublet 2' proton (T 2.35) and a singlet proton at C-4 (T 2.33) – the last two signals and that due to C-5 proton overlapping somewhat with each other. The absence of signal due to C-3 proton in the region T 3.5 - 3.8 and appearance of the C-4 proton as a singlet indicated that the remaining C_6H_9 residue should be attached to the only possible site, C-3 of the furanocoumarin moiety. The other signals in the spectrum of xylotenin coming from this side chain, consisted of an ABX system, clearly visible in the olefinic region (H_A , T 4.91, quartet ; H_B , T 4.89, quartet ; H_X , T 3.37, quartet : $J_{AX} =$

* Presented at the Chemistry Section of the 55th Session of the Indian Science Congress, Varanasi, on January 7, 1968.

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† Mass spectra were determined with an AEI MS-9 spectrometer using a direct insertion probe and operating at 70 eV.

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18.0 c./sec., $J_{BX}=10.5$ c./sec., $J_{AB}=2$ c./sec.) assigned to a vinyl group attached to the trisubstituted carbon atom (see structure I) bearing two equivalent methyl groups appearing as a sharp singlet (T 8.50, 6 H). This led to the formulation of the C_6H_9 side chain as a 1,1-dimethylallyl group and the structure of xylothenin as (I).

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

Xylothenin, when hydrogenated in glacial acetic acid or ethanol over palladium-charcoal (10%) absorbed 2 moles of hydrogen in about an hour to yield tetrahydroxyxylothenin (II), $C_{16}H_{18}O_8$ (M^+ 258), m.p. 183-84°, ν_{max} (nujol) 1700 (coumarin CO), 1580 (α -pyrone double bond), 1625 cm^{-1} (aromatic); no strong band at 880 cm^{-1} . Prolonged exposure to hydrogen in ethanol over palladium-charcoal (10%) produced hexahydroxyxylothenin (III), $C_{16}H_{20}O_8$ (M^+ 260), m.p. 115-16°, in which the terminal methylene and both the furan and the α -pyrone double bonds of xylothenin were saturated, as evident from the spectral data: λ_{max} (ethanol) 290 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 1.77); λ_{min} 265 (1.23), ν_{max} (nujol) 1755 cm^{-1} (CO of dihydrocoumarin system) and 1615 and 1628 cm^{-1} (aromatic); the bands at 1580 and 880 cm^{-1} , discernible in the spectrum of xylothenin, were absent. Confirmation of the structure of the side chain in (I) was also secured from the NMR spectrum of hexahydroxyxylothenin (III). The ABX system in the olefinic region disappeared and instead, a group of bands appeared as a quartet (T 8.48, 2 H) and a triplet (T 9.17, 3 H) ($J=7$ c./sec.) forming an A_2B_3 system and corresponding to an ethyl chain bonded to a trisubstituted carbon. The gem-Me groups, as expected, were shifted to higher field and appeared as two sharp singlets (T 9.03, 8.97, 3 H each). Only two 1 H singlets appeared in the aromatic region due to protons on C-5 (T 3.06—slightly broadened by long range coupling with proton on C-3') and C-8 (T 3.55). No furan protons were visible, but the 2' and 3' methylenes of the dihydrofuran system were seen as triplets (T 5.43 and 6.87 respectively, $J=9$ c./sec.). A complex multiplet in the region T 7.05 - 7.67 (3H) were attributable to protons on C-3 and C-4.

Xylotenin, upon refluxing in dry benzene in presence of hydrogen chloride gas and anhydrous aluminium chloride, was converted to a crystalline compound, m.p. 190-91°. M^+ 370, λ_{\max} (ethanol) 340 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.02), the characterisation of which is currently in progress.

The mass spectra of xylotenin (I), tetrahydroxylotenin (II) and hexahydroxylotenin (III) are also in agreement with proposed structures. Both xylotenin (I) and heliaddin (IV ; M^+ 314), like the parent furanocoumarin psoralene and unlike its angular isomer angelicin⁵, exhibited molecular ions as the base peaks. The other principal peaks [$M-15$ and $M-15-28$] were due to ions derived by loss of a tertiary methyl group at the doubly allylic position (see I and IV) and subsequent expulsion of $CO^{5,6}$. A small $M-27$ (loss of $-CH=CH_2$) peak, a strong $M-27-28$ (loss of $-CH=CH_2$ and CO) peak in the mass spectra of both (I) and (IV), and a very small $M-69$ (loss of C_6H_9 side chain) peak in the spectrum of I are also consistent with the assigned structures. Fission of the hydroxylated side chain in heliaddin (IV) with charge retention on either side produced ions appearing at m/e 59 ($Me_2C=O^+H$) and m/e 255 ($M-59$). Another significant ion with m/e 241 was produced from M^+-CH_3 ion of heliaddin by the expulsion of the hydroxylated side chain with simultaneous hydrogen capture; subsequent loss of CO gave rise to the peak at m/e 213. Loss of the ethyl group in II and cleavage at 'a' with hydrogen capture in III corresponded to their base peaks at m/e 229 and 149 respectively. Further details of the mass spectra and the reactions of xylotenin will be published in a full paper.

Heliaddin was reported⁷ very recently from another *Rutaceae* plant *Helietta longifoliata* Britt and its mass spectral fragmentation pattern lends further support to its suggested structure (IV).

Xylotenin is the first example of a 3-substituted furanocoumarin having no oxygen function at C-4. Occurrence of 7-demethyl suberosin⁸, heliaddin and xylotenin in the same plant is biogenetically significant.

This investigation was supported in part by the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, and by the University Grants Commission, India.

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Received July 18, 1968.

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